

NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF DATE PALM FRUIT (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) AS SUGAR SUBSTITUTE IN THE PRODUCTION OF ENRICHED CORN FLOUR, YELLOW FLESH SWEET POTATOES FLOUR AND COWPEA FLOUR

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ABSTRACT

Prevalence of diet-related diseases among children and adolescents have been linked to high consumption of refined sugar and this has called for the use of sugar substitute. The proximate analyses and sensory evaluation of cookies made from a blend of corn, yellow sweet potatoes, cowpea and date palm as sugar substitutes were carried out. All the materials were processed into flour and used in producing the cookies in the ratios: 50:5:15:30, 60:10:10:20, 70:0:15:25, 70:5:10:15, 80:5:5:10 and 100:0:0:0; all labeled as samples A, B, C, D, E and F respectively. Proximate properties of moisture, crude protein, crude fiber, crude fat, ash content and carbohydrate of the cookies were determined using the Association of Official Agricultural Chemists (AOAC, 2003) method. Sensory evaluation was determined by a group of trained panelists from the Department of Home Economics and Hotel Management, Tai Solarin University of Education Ogun State, Nigeria. Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). Means were separated using Duncan New Multiple Range Test. Statistical significance was considered at p-values ≤ 0.05 . An increase in fat (8.05%-10.48%), ash (1.63%-2.94%), fibre (3.19%-3.85%) and protein (8.07%-10.88%) contents were observed as the proportion of date and cowpea flour increased. Carbohydrate and moisture content decreased with an increase in the proportion of date and cowpea flour. Both the enriched and non-enriched cookies were well accepted. Cookies using date as a sugar substitute can be produced from different blends of composite flours to enrich it.

Keywords: Corn; Yellow flesh sweet potatoes; Date palm; Cookies, Proximate properties; Sensory evaluation

INTRODUCTION

Childhood and adolescent malnutrition is on the increase, especially among the Low and Middle Income Countries (LMIC) of the world. The majority has been associated with snacking replacing breakfast (Ayogu *et al.*, 2016) and one of the most frequently consumed snacks among school children and adolescents is cookies. Contemporary cookies are unhealthy snacks that are generally made with refined sugar, refined wheat flour and fat which are often unhealthy fats. Cookies are

expected to be sweet and most commercial products certainly contain a lot of sugar; the amount of sugar per serving is certain to have quite an effect on blood sugar levels. To remain cost-competitive in today's dynamic and economic environment, nutritionists must be willing and prepared to switch to alternate series grain sources at various levels of inclusion (Steve, 2015). Cookies can therefore be produced from these variations. Corns are used in the production of several traditional food, it is mainly composed of carbohydrate

and has small amounts of protein and fat. Corn flour is generally easy to digest; it contains valuable antioxidants and provides decent protein and fiber. The yellow corn cultivar is more important because of its richness in Beta-carotene, a pro-vitamin A that enhances good eyesight in children and adults (Igbabul *et al.*, 2014). Although, wheat flour is generally used for snacking but it has limitations in some cases which include the situation of dietary intolerance of wheat known as coeliac disease as reviewed by Tatham and Shewery (2015). Other problems associated with wheat consumption are respiratory and food allergies, and asthma which is considered as one of the most important forms of allergy (Gayathri and Rashmi, 2016). Processing sweet potato into flour could increase its utilization. The processed flour can then serve as a source of nutrients such as carbohydrates, beta-carotene (pro-vitamin A), vitamin C, vitamin B₆, calcium, phosphorus, iron, potassium, magnesium and zinc (Obayendo, 2017). This can contribute to the colour, flavour and dietary fibre of processed food products such as bread, it also enhances its use in other food preparation.

Date is a delicious fruit with a sweet taste and flashy mouth feel. The major components of dates are carbohydrates (mainly sugars; glucose, and fructose), which may constitute about 70% of what of these sugars. The sugars in date are easily digested and can immediately be moved to the blood after consumption and can quickly be metabolized to release energy for various cell activities (Dada *et al.*, 2012). Dates are also good sources of fiber and contain many important vitamins and minerals, including significant amounts of calcium, iron, fluorine, and selenium (Ali *et al.*, 2012). Legumes are a class of vegetables that includes beans, peas and lentils, legumes are typically low in fat, contain no cholesterol, high in potassium, iron, and magnesium. They also contain insoluble and soluble fiber and are a good source of protein (Mayo, 2018). The main important characteristics of these crops include a good protein quality with a high nutritional value (Marcia *et al.*, 2017).

Date powder used at varying proportions for the replacement of sugar in the formulation of biscuit showed the highest acceptability at 30% incorporation of date powder, also, at this proportion, an increase in ash and crude fiber content was observed (Latif and Pik, 2023). In the production of cookies using: potato flour enriched with date palm fruit powder and bean milk, three different samples were formulated: potato flour with date powder and bean milk (PDBM), potato flour with sugar and bean milk (PSBM), and potato flour, sugar, and eggs (PSE) as control respectively. The results showed an increase in the protein, carbohydrate and fat contents in the order: PDBM>PSBM>PSG, and the organoleptic characteristics of PDBM and PSBM were rated overall best when specific parameters were tested. The study thus concluded that with the shortage of wheat and importation constraints, alternatives that can provide a great market opportunity for local products like potatoes and beans can be used. Also, fortifying food products such as cookies eaten by all will contribute to a more food and nutrition-secured world (Akhobakoh *et al.*, 2022). The effect of date powder as a natural sweetener in place of sugar on the proximate chemical composition, physical properties and sensory characterizations of cookies was evaluated at varying proportions of 5%, 10%, 20%, and 40% of date powder, respectively. The obtained results showed that increasing the proportion of the date powder led to an increase in total carbohydrates, crude fibers, ash, crude fat, moisture and protein contents. However, physical characteristics of cookies, i.e. thickness, diameter and speed factor of the prepared cookies decreased. The findings of the study also ascertained that the cookies supplemented with 40% date powder had the lowest acceptability. Meanwhile, at a substitution ratio of 10%, the quality of cookies was not adversely affected by the color, taste, crispiness, texture, odor and overall acceptability ($p \geq 0.05$), so, it could suggest that date palm powder can be used and incorporated in bakery products up to 10% (Aya Abdl El-Nasser, Abdel Fattah Elkalyoubi and El-

Sharabasy, 2020). Hyelsinta and Maijalo (2016) investigated the physicochemical and acceptability of cookies as affected by cereals and legume type by producing cookies from millet, rice, sorghum and cowpea flour blends in a bid to increase the protein quality and promote the utilization of local raw materials. The result of the study showed a significant increase in protein content of the cookies ranging from 11.06 to 15.84%. Ikuomola *et al.* (2017) have also assessed the quality of cookies produced from cowpea flour and malted barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) bran blends. The results vividly showed that it could be possible to produce nutritious and acceptable cookies through the substitution of wheat flour with malted barley bran. The high protein, ash and fibre contents of cookies made from malted barley bran substitution as well as the acceptability of the composite cookies attested to this fact. Protein increased from 11.21–15.64%, ash: 1.14 - 1.88%, fibre: 1.32 - 6.38%. Ikechukwu *et al.* (2017) investigated the production and evaluation of cookies from whole wheat flour and date palm fruit pulp as sugar substitutes. The use of date palm fruit as a sugar substitute in cookie production improved the properties of the flours such as swelling index, oil absorption capacity, pH and viscosity as they were comparable to the control (refined wheat flour). The proximate

composition of cookies increased with an increase in the percentage of palm pulp in the cookies and the samples were comparable to the control (100% wheat flour) except in protein content where the control was very high. Adeyeye *et al.*, (2017) assessed the quality and sensory properties of maize flour cookies enriched with soy protein isolate to encourage the use of soybeans in producing value-added products. The results revealed that the substitution of maize flour with soy protein isolate significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increased the protein from $8.69 \pm 0.19\%$ to $29.11 \pm 0.34\%$. This study, however, sought to combine enriched cookies with legumes to further increase protein content and use date palm fruit as sugar substitute.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The raw materials for the research were corn, cowpeas, sweet potatoes and date. These materials except date fruit were purchased from Oke-Aje market in Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria. The date was sweet, oblong rounded apex, golden brown and was reportedly harvested at the early stage of development (Doka stage). The skin was thin, shrunken with flesh irregular wrinkles. It was obtained from Kabiru farm, Knakachi, Kano State, Nigeria

Flow chart for the processing of raw materials into flour

Sources: Adeyeye *et al.*, 2017 ; Ndife *et al.*, 2014

Flow chat for the processing of date palm

Source: Ikehukwu *et al.*, 2017

Preparation of the Cookies

The processed flour (200g each) was measured in a bowl. Using the rubbing method, fat, milk and salt were added and rubbed for 30 minutes in a separate bowl, egg and water were mixed and added to the flour-based mixture and kneaded and made into dough. The dough was rolled and flattened into a uniform thickness of about 3.5 mm before being cut out into shapes

using a hand-cutter. The cutout dough was baked at 150 °C for 30 minutes in the oven. After baking, the cookies were cooled to room temperature, packed in low-density polyethylene (LDPE) bags and sealed in a plastic transparent container. This procedure was used as outlined in Chinwendu and Kabuo (2017).

Table 1: The recipe for fortified and unfortified cookies

Fortifiedcookies/Unfortifiedcookies	Quantity
Flour (corn/yellow flesh sweet potato/cowpea/ date)	200(g)
Margarine	80(g)
Sugar (for unfortified cookies)	60(g)
Baking powder	2(g)
Whole egg	3pieces
Salt	2(g)
Flavour	4 drops
Water	30ml

Adapted from Ikechukwu *et al.*,2017

Table 2: Composition and amount (g) of different samples of the produced cookies

Sample(s)	Corn flour(g)	Sweet potatoes Flour(g)	Cowpea flour(g)	Date fruit flour(g)
(CF+SW+CPF+DF)A	50%(100g)	5%(10g)	15%(30g)	30%(60g)
(CF+SW+CPF+DF)B	60%(120g)	10%(20g)	10%(20g)	20%(40g)
(CF+CPF+DF)C	70%(140g)	-	15%(30g)	25%(50g)
(CF+SW+CPF+DF)D	70%(140g)	10%(20g)	5%(10g)	15%(30g)
(CF+SW+CPF+DF)E	80(160g)	5%(10g)	5%(10g)	10%(20g)
(CF)F	Corn flour 100%(200g)	-	-	-

Note:

CF = Corn flour

SW =Sweet potato flour

CPF = Cowpea flour

DF = Date fruit flour

Proximate Determination

Moisture content of the cookies

The moisture content was determined by weighing out 2g of the samples into a dry crucible of known mass, and charred into the oven at a temperature of 105°C for 3 hours. The samples were cooled in a desiccator and weighed using an electronic analytical balance. The whole process was repeated until a constant mass was obtained.

The difference in mass (weight of % moisture lost) was calculated as % moisture content =

$$\frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_2 - W_1} \times 100$$

Where: W_1 = weight of empty crucible

W_2 = weight of crucible + sample before drying

W_3 = weight of crucible + sample after drying to constant mass.

Protein content of the cookies

The Kjeldhal method, (N x 6.25) as described by AOAC (2003) was used. The total Nitrogen was determined using the conversion factor of 6.25. About 2 g of the samples were boiled in 10ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 in the presence of selenium catalyst (one tablespoonful). Boiling was done under a fume cupboard until a clear solution was formed. The digest was transferred into a volumetric flask containing 100ml of distilled water and 10ml of it was mixed with equal volumes of 45% NaOH

solution and was poured into a Kjeldhal distillate apparatus. After distilling the mixture, the distillate was collected in a 100ml of 4% boric acid solution containing 3 drops of a mixed indicator (methyl red and bromo cresol green). A total of 50ml of distillate was collected and titrated against 0.02N H_2SO_4 solution. Titration was done from green to a deep red endpoint. A reagent blank was determined as described above but without the sample. The protein content (N_2) was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen, } N_2 = \frac{V_S - V_B \times N_A \times 0.01401}{W} \times 100$$

Where: V_S = Volume (ml) of acid required to titrate sample

V_B = Volume (ml) of acid required to titrate blank

N_A = Normality of acid

W = Weight of Samples in grams

% Crude Protein = N_2 x conversion factor

Fat content of the cookies

The solvent extraction method of AOAC (2003) was used. A soxhlet extraction unit was set up with a reflux condenser. A small round bottom flask was weighed after washing and drying and half filled with light petroleum ether (boiling point 40 – 60°C) and fixed into the unit. 2g of each of the samples were wrapped in Whatmann filter paper and gradually lowered into the thimble which was

filled to the cleaned, dried and weighed round bottom flask containing 120ml of N-hexane. Fat was extracted for 6 hours using the petroleum ether and was recovered by distillation. After evaporating off of the solvent, the flask was dried in the oven at 105°C, cooled in a desiccator and weighed to determine the amount of lipid extracted. By difference, the mass of oil extracted was determined and thus expressed as

$$\% \text{ Fat} = \frac{W_3 - W_2}{W_1} \times 100$$

Where, W_3 is the weight of the flask with the extracted oil

W_2 is the weight of the empty flask

W_1 is the weight of the sample.

Ash content of the cookies

Ash content was determined using AOAC, 2003 by furnace incineration, weighing 2g of each of the sample into a porcelain crucible of known mass, heating in moisture extraction oven (muffle furnace) at 550°C for 3 hours until

it completely ashed that is turned white and free of carbon. The sample were then removed from the furnace, cooled in a dessicator to a room temperature and reweighed immediately. The weight of the ash (residual ash) was then calculated as

$$\% \text{ Ash (dry basis)} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Weight of original sample}} \times 100$$

$$\frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{Weight of original sample}} \times 100$$

Where: W1 = Weight of Empty crucible
W2 = Weight of crucible + Ash

Crude fibre content of the cookies

Crude fibre was determined by AOAC (2003) method. About 1 g of each sample was weighed into 600 ml of Erlenmeyer flask; 100 ml of trichloroacetic acid digestion reagent was added. The solution was brought to boil and reflux for exactly 40 min at 50–60°C counting from the time boiling started. The flask was removed from the heater, cooled a little bit and was filtered through a 15.0 cm, Whatman filter paper of 1.0 g, the residue was

washed six times with hot water and once with methylated spirit. The residue was removed by spatula from the opened-out filter paper, and the fibre was transferred into a porcelain dish and was dried overnight at 500°C. The sample was transferred to a desiccator and weighed when cool; it was washed in a muffle furnace at 600°C for 6 h. This was cooled again and reweighed. Finally, the percent crude fibre was determined by the following formula:

$$\% \text{ Crude fibre} = \frac{\text{Weight after drying} - \text{weight after washing}}{\text{Sample weight}} \times 100$$

Carbohydrates

The carbohydrate was calculated as weight by a difference between 100 and the summation of other proximate parameters as percentage carbohydrate.

$$\% \text{ carbohydrate} = 100 - (\% \text{ moisture} + \% \text{ protein} + \% \text{ fat} + \% \text{ fat} + \% \text{ fibre})$$

acceptability were evaluated by a panelist. Responses gathered from panelists were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), means were separated using Duncan New Multiple Ranged Test

Sensory Evaluation

Sensory evaluation was determined using twenty-five students from the Department of Home Economics and Hotel Management, Tai Solarin University of Education Ijebu-Ode, Ogun, Nigeria. The 9-point hedonic scale was used as from 9 - like extremely, 5-neither like nor dislike and 1-dislike extremely. The sensory attributes of the products, including colour, taste, flavor/aroma, texture and overall

RESULTS

Table 3 shows an increase in the moisture and carbohydrate contents as the proportion of corn flour increased. The moisture content of the cookies ranged between 15.80% and 20.77% while carbohydrates ranged between 55.49% and 58.11%. Cookies made with 100% corn flour had the highest value of moisture content (20.77%) and carbohydrate (58.11%). There was no significant difference in the moisture content of samples B and D. Also, a non-

significant difference was equally observed in the carbohydrate contents of samples B C D E respectively. Fat, ash, fibre and crude protein contents of the cookies decreased as the proportion of the corn flour increased and

cookies made with 50% corn flour had the highest values, though a non-significant difference in the fibre contents of samples A B C D were observed.

Table 3: proximate composition of the produced cookies

Sample	Moisture content	Dry matter content	Fat content	Ash content	Crude fibre content	Crude protein content	Carbohydrate content
A	15.80 ^e	78.23 ^e	10.48 ^a	2.94 ^a	3.85 ^a	10.88 ^a	55.49 ^c
B	17.32 ^c	81.41 ^d	9.85 ^b	1.90 ^b	3.83 ^a	10.11 ^b	57.45 ^b
C	16.86 ^d	82.39 ^c	9.84 ^b	1.88 ^c	3.80 ^a	10.08 ^b	57.53 ^b
D	17.61 ^c	83.64 ^b	9.42 ^c	1.84 ^c	3.80 ^a	9.63 ^c	57.56 ^b
E	18.39 ^b	82.68 ^c	9.22 ^c	1.73 ^d	3.75 ^b	9.43 ^c	57.71 ^b
F	20.77 ^a	84.80 ^a	8.05 ^d	1.63 ^d	3.19 ^c	8.07 ^d	58.55 ^a

Note: Proximate analysis results are in g/100g sample. Means within a column with the same superscript were not significantly different ($P>0.05$)

Table 4. Sensory Evaluation Table of the Cookies

Samples	Taste	Aroma	Crispness	Colour	Texture	General Acceptability
A	7.16±1.72 ^{ab}	7.52±1.45 ^{ab}	7.12±1.62 ^b	6.92±1.63 ^c	7.52±1.66 ^b	7.44±1.58 ^{ab}
B	7.96±1.70 ^a	7.84±1.70 ^b	7.56±1.69 ^{ab}	7.60±1.44 ^b	7.84±1.68 ^a	7.64±1.71 ^{ab}
C	7.88±1.64 ^a	7.68±1.41 ^{ab}	7.60±1.61 ^{ab}	7.92±1.26 ^b	7.48±1.83 ^{ab}	7.92±1.63 ^a
D	7.84±1.55 ^a	7.80±1.32 ^b	7.80±1.56 ^{ab}	7.88±1.36 ^b	7.92±1.58 ^a	7.88±1.42 ^a
E	7.60±1.53 ^a	7.52±1.23 ^{ab}	7.36±1.58 ^b	7.96±1.17 ^b	7.68±1.41 ^{ab}	7.56±1.61 ^{ab}
F	7.88±1.51 ^a	8.00±1.23 ^a	8.00±1.16 ^a	8.40±0.87 ^a	8.08±1.29 ^a	8.20±1.16

Table 4 describes the sensory results of the cookies. Sample B (50% corn flour, 5% sweet potatoes flour, 15% cowpea flour and 30% date flour) had the highest score (7.96±1.70) for taste and was not significantly different from samples C, D, E and F. The aroma of the cookies ranged from 7.52±1.45 to 8.00±1.23 and there was no significant difference between the aroma of samples B and D. Also, a non-

significant difference was observed in the aroma of samples A, C and E. Crispness of the cookies ranged between 7.12±1.62 to 8.00±1.16 and sample F had the highest score. There was an increase in the crispness of the cookies as the proportion of the corn flour increased and a non-significant difference between samples A and E, and among samples B, C and D respectively. The intensity of the

colour of the cookies also increased as the proportion of the corn flour increased and there was no significant difference between samples B, C, D and E. The texture of the cookies was rated like very much and like moderately with only sample F (100% corn flour) being liked very much. Nevertheless, a non-significant difference in the texture of samples B, D and F was observed. Also, there was no significant difference in the texture of samples C and E. Cookies prepared with 100% corn flour (sample F) had the best overall general acceptability, although, there was no significant difference between this sample and samples C and D. There was also no significant difference between samples A, B and E. Hence, the substitution of date palm fruit and cowpea should not be less than 15% date palm fruit and 5% cowpea. Also, the substitution should not be more than 20% date palm fruit and 10% cowpea

DISCUSSION

The results of the proximate analyses revealed a decrease in the moisture and fibre content in the samples as shown in Table 3. A higher value for moisture and fibre was recorded for cookies made with 100% corn flour and with date palm fruit as a sugar substitute. Ikechukwu *et al.*, 2017 also reported a decrease in fibre content of cookies produced from whole wheat and date palm fruit pulp as sugar substitute as the date substitute increased. Fat content of the cookies also increased as the proportion of the corn flour increased. This ranged from 8.65% to 10.16% with sample F (100% corn flour) having the lowest value and sample A having the highest value. This is against the findings of Adeyeye *et al.*, 2017 who reported highest value of fat content in cookies produced from 100% maize flour and a decrease in value as the maize flour content decreased. The protein content of the flour samples ranged from 8.91% to 10.11%. The highest value of protein was observed in sample A (10.11), and the lowest value was reported in sample F (100% corn flour). This might be due to the presence of

cowpea serving as an increased in source of protein. Aluko, Brai and Adelore (2013) also reported an increase in the protein content of cookies produced from maize-incorporated moringa as the proportion of the moringa flour increased. Ash content ranged between 1.73% and 2.04% with sample F(100% corn flour) having the lowest value and sample A having the highest value. Date has been reported to be rich in minerals owing to the highest value of ash content in sample A ((Ali, Waly, Essa and Devarajan, 2012). Table 4 revealed the sensory results of the cookies. Sample B (50% corn flour, 5% sweet potatoes flour, 15% cowpea flour and 30% date flour) had the highest score (7.96 ± 1.70) for taste while sample A had the lowest score(7.16 ± 1.72). This is in line with the findings of Ikechukwu *et al.*, 2017 who reported the highest score for the taste of cookies in a sample with 100% refined wheat flour (with sugar added according to the standard cookie recipe) and the minimum score in the sample with the lowest proportion of date flour as a sugar substitute. The score of the aroma of the cookies ranged between 7.52 ± 1.23 and 8.00 ± 1.23 with sample F (100% corn flour) having the maximum score (8.00 ± 1.23) and the minimum score was sample E and B (7.84 ± 1.70 and 7.84 ± 1.70) respectively. The highest score for sample F may be due to the non-inclusion of other materials (sweet potato, cowpea and date flour) in the production of cookies. This is against the result of maize-incorporated moringa in the production of cookies reported by Aluko *et al.*, 2013. The maximum score for the aroma of the cookies was observed in the blend having the highest incorporation of moringa (7.5% moringa). The crispness of the cookies ranged from 7.12 ± 1.62 to 8.00 ± 1.16 with sample F (100% wheat flour) having a maximum crispness value (8.00 ± 1.16) and the minimum value observed in cookies prepared from sample A (7.12 ± 1.62). Ikuomola *et al.*, 2017 also reported the highest score of crispness in a sample with 100% wheat flour and the lowest score in a sample with 50% wheat flour 50% malted barley bran. Colour is a very important parameter in judging properly baked cookies

that not only reflects the suitable raw materials used for the preparation but also provides information about the formulation and quality of the product. Ikpeme, Osuchukwu and Oshieel (2010) also reported that colour attribute is a major criterion that affects the quality of baked products. The colour of cookies ranged from 6.92 ± 1.63 to 8.40 ± 0.87 . An increase in the intensity of colour of the cookies was observed as the proportion of the corn flour increased. Sample F (100% corn flour) had the highest score (8.40 ± 0.87) while sample A had the lowest score (6.92 ± 1.63). Sample F had the highest texture content with a mean score of 8.08 ± 1.29 , and sample A had the lowest value (7.52 ± 1.66). This is in line with the result of the study of Ndife *et al.*, 2014 who investigated the production and quality assessment of enriched cookies from whole wheat and full-fat soya and reported that the scores for the texture of the cookie samples were affected by soybean flour substitution. The cookie with 30% soy flour substitution, had the best score (8.10) for texture. Cookies prepared with 100% corn flour (sample F) had the highest acceptability at 8.20 ± 1.16 while the least acceptable was sample A. Ikuomola *et al.*, 2017 also reported the highest score of general acceptability in the sample with 100% wheat flour and the lowest score in a sample with 50% wheat flour 50% malted barley bran.

CONCLUSION

Both fortified and unfortified cookies were well accepted though at different levels. Cookies produced with a maximum proportion of cowpea using 30% date palm fruit (sample A) had the highest fat, ash and protein contents while sample F (control: 100% corn flour) had the highest moisture, dry matter, fibre and carbohydrate content. Sample F had the highest acceptability and sample A had the lowest. Nutritional incorporation of date palm fruit, cowpea and yellow flesh sweet potato in the production of enriched cookies is recommended as some of the nutrients were found to have increased. Consuming this type of cookies can help eradicate nutritional problems of high intake of artificial sweeteners and low protein intake.

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